

Identification and Verification of a New Reference Rod for Enhanced Burn-up Calculations at Studsvik: A Comprehensive Evaluation and Comparative Analysis

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Abstract

The changing requirements of modern Light Water Reactors (LWRs) underscore the limitations of the F3F6 rod used in Studsvik for burn-up calculation from Gamma scan data. Therefore, a thorough evaluation was necessary to address these issues and find a more suitable standard for industrial use. This study addresses the need for improved burn-up calculations on fuel segments in Studsvik by introducing and validating a new reference rod, called R3D12. This proposed replacement for the F3F6 rod, which has been used to map local burn-up values in fuel segments for years. To characterize R3D12 and confirm its performance, a state-of-the-art gamma scanning technique, particularly focusing on circumferential gamma scanning, is used. This approach provides a detail and precise analysis of isotopic distributions and burn-up profiles within the fuel segments. A comparison between the F3F6 and R3D12 rods reveals several key advantages of the R3D12 rod for modern LWR applications. Notably, R3D12 demonstrates greater result consistency, a smaller margin of error, and better alignment with newer and higher industrial standards in the post-Fukushima era. The study also investigates methods to enhance the accuracy of burn-up calculations from Gamma scan data. An experimental toolkit developed in Python incorporates advanced algorithms that enable flexible adjustments to accommodate various fuel types and discharge conditions. Additionally, it includes features for integrating and analyzing complex datasets, thereby streamlining the calculation process, and reducing the potential for human errors.

Keywords— burn-up, gamma scanning, FIMA, Cs-137

I. INTRODUCTION

As one of the fundamental parameters of nuclear engineering, burn-up (BU) calculations are crucial for the safety and efficiency of nuclear reactors. In simple terms, burn-up represents the amount of energy extracted from nuclear fuel during its stay in a reactor. Several critical factors are directly influenced by this parameter, including fuel management strategies, waste disposal protocols and overall reactor safety, demonstrating that burn-up calculations are not just a measure of fuel consumption but are also integral to the operational integrity and longevity of nuclear reactors. As it impacts the operational integrity and longevity of nuclear reactors.

Accurate burn-up assessments are essential in nuclear reactors to optimize fuel cycles, minimize the long-lived radioactive waste and ensure proper safety margins during operation. Given the intricate nature of these calculations—due to the numerous variables involved, such as neutron flux, fuel composition, and irradiation time—they must be performed with a high degree of accuracy to account for the complex interactions within the reactor core. A crucial component in the burn-up calculation process at Studsvik is the selection of a reference rod, which serves as the baseline for all measurements. The company prioritizes using the most economical

and non-destructive methods for burn-up calculations, making the accurate characterization of the reference rod essential. Any errors or uncertainties in this characterization could lead to cascading inaccuracies throughout the entire burn-up calculation process, highlighting the importance of selecting an appropriate reference rod.

The F3F6 rod for burn-up calculations was first used at Studsvik to study fuel behavior in the Light Water Reactor (LWR) and in Post Irradiation Review projects for the customer. However, with the increasing in fuel burnup values and the emergence of new generation nuclear technologies, there is an increasing need to update and improve the reference rod (in this case F3F6) used for burnup calculations. While setting a new reference rod, Studsvik, recognizing the need for more suitable rods to better fit modern fuel design and meet the demands associated with higher burn rate fuels, initiated a study.

The Studsvik Father Rod Library, including F3F6, is a resource that provides a comprehensive, digitized collection of technical details and enrichment ratios for fuel rods from various reactors and designs worldwide.

The main features of this library are as follows;

Extensive Data Records: Each reference rod entry in

the library is accompanied by detailed data regarding its production history, materials used, and various measurements taken over time. This wealth of information not only supports current research and aids in the planning and execution of future projects.

Advanced Search and Filtering Capabilities: The library is equipped with sophisticated tools that allow users to search and filter reference rods according to specific criteria relevant to their research or operational needs. These capabilities are particularly useful in identifying suitable reference rods for burn-up calculations and other complex analyses.

Historical and Performance Data: In addition to technical specifications, the library also contains records of the historical use and performance of each reference rod. This includes data on accuracy and reliability over time, which is crucial for selecting appropriate reference rods for current and future applications.

This study aims to establish a new reference rod that meets the stringent requirements of modern designs and to lay the groundwork for more accurate burn-up calculations. This involves three key tasks:

Identification of Candidate Reference Rods: A comprehensive review of Studsvik's rod library was conducted, with specific criteria developed in collaboration with nuclear engineering experts. These criteria guided the filtering and selection process, ultimately leading to the identification of potential reference rod candidates.

Comparative Analysis: The study undertook a detailed comparative analysis between the current reference rod (F3F6) and the new candidate (R3D12). This analysis utilized a range of measurement techniques, including advanced gamma scanning and computational tools, to highlight the differences and assess the suitability of R3D12 as the new reference rod.

Develop pioneer tool for data analysis: An automated toolkit written in Python was developed to guide user to input and analyses the data automatically.

II. STUDY ON MEASUREMENT METHODS AND ANALYSIS

This section delves into how gamma scanning is used to measure the local axial burn-up of nuclear fuel rods. Gamma scanning focuses on Cesium-137 (Cs-137) emissions, which help assess burn-up levels along the length of the rod. By using high-resolution scanning techniques, variations in fission product distribution can be detected, allowing for precise burn-up calculations. The axial measurements help identify any irregularities or hot spots in the fuel, which is critical for ensuring safe and efficient reactor operation

A. Burn-up Measurement Techniques

Burn-up, a measure of the energy produced by nuclear fuel, is an essential parameter in nuclear reactor operation, influencing everything from fuel management to safety protocols. Accurate burn-up measurement is crucial for determining the amount of fissionable material consumed in a reactor, thereby informing decisions about fuel replacement,

reactor performance, and safety. Several techniques have been developed to measure burn-up, each with its advantages and limitations. Several techniques have been developed to measure burn-up, each with its own advantages and limitations. One widely used method is gamma spectroscopy, which involves analyzing the gamma radiation emitted by fission products within spent nuclear fuel. Gamma-emitting isotopes such as Cesium-137 (Cs-137) are of particular interest due to their abundance and relatively long half-life of 30.7 years, which provides a consistent signal for measurement over time [1]. By measuring the intensity of gamma rays emitted from Cs-137, the burn-up of nuclear fuel can be estimated with reasonable accuracy. Gamma spectroscopy is advantageous because it is non-destructive, meaning the fuel rod remains intact during analysis, preserving its structural integrity and allowing for continuous monitoring. As shown in Fig.1 a Boiling Water Reactor (BWR) fuel assembly before and after burn-up highlights the arrangement of fuel rods and the general layout. This method is complemented by other non-destructive techniques, such as neutron interrogation, which provides additional information about isotopic distributions and minor actinides within the fuel. However, for the highest precision, gamma spectroscopy measurements are sometimes validated against destructive radiochemical analysis, where fuel samples are chemically dissolved to directly measure isotopic concentrations [2]. This validation process is particularly important for calibrating gamma spectroscopy equipment and methods to ensure their accuracy in routine operations.

Figure 1: BWR Fuel Assembly Before and After Burn-Up .

Another significant technique used in burn-up measurement is the fission gas release method, where the amount of gas released from the fuel is measured to estimate burn-up. This method, however, is less commonly used compared to gamma spectroscopy due to its invasive nature and the challenges associated with accurately quantifying the gas released during reactor operation. Despite the utility of these techniques, there are inherent challenges. Factors such as the initial fuel composition, reactor operating conditions, and the geometric configuration of the fuel rods can introduce uncertainties in burn-up measurements [3]. To mitigate these uncertainties, advanced computational models have been developed to simulate reactor conditions and predict burn-up more accurately. These models use data from gamma spectroscopy and other

measurement techniques to refine their predictions, making them a valuable tool for nuclear engineers. Fig.2 illustrates the complex arrangement of fuel rods within a 17x17 Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) fuel assembly, both before and after burn-up.

Figure 2: PWR Fuel Assembly Before and After Burn-Up .

B. Advancements in Gamma Scanning Technology

Gamma scanning technology has evolved significantly, particularly with the development of circumferential gamma scanning methods. Circumferential gamma scanning involves rotating the fuel rod and taking gamma measurements at multiple angles around its circumference. This technique offers a more comprehensive analysis of the fuel rod's isotopic composition, as it can detect variations in gamma emissions that are not apparent when using traditional axial gamma scanning methods [4].

Fig.3 provides a close-up view of a single fuel rod, highlighting its structural features and the materials used in its construction. Circumferential gamma scanning is particularly valuable for identifying asymmetries in the fuel rod that could lead to inaccuracies in burn-up calculations. By providing a 360-degree view of the fuel rod's gamma emissions, this method allows for the detection of subtle variations in isotopic concentration, which are critical for accurate burn-up assessment [5]. For example, small differences in fuel composition or density can significantly affect the distribution of fission products within the rod, leading to potential errors in burn-up calculations if not properly accounted for.

Figure 3: A fuel rod.

In recent years, the integration of circumferential gamma scanning with advanced data processing techniques has further enhanced its capabilities. Modern gamma scanning systems are equipped with sophisticated software that can analyze large datasets in real-time, integrating measurements from multiple angles to produce a detailed isotopic profile of the fuel rod [6]. This level of detail is crucial for applications such as selecting reference rods for burn-up calculations, where even minor inaccuracies can have significant implications for reactor safety and efficiency. The importance of accurate reference rod selection cannot be overstated. The reference rod serves as the standard against which burn-up is measured, and any errors in its characterization can propagate through the entire burn-up measurement process, leading to inaccurate results [7]. Circumferential gamma scanning helps mitigate this risk by providing a thorough and detailed analysis of the reference rod's isotopic composition, ensuring that it accurately reflects the characteristics of the fuel rods being assessed.

In conclusion, the advancements in gamma scanning technology, particularly the adoption of circumferential scanning methods, have significantly enhanced the accuracy and reliability of burn-up measurements. These technological developments are essential for ensuring the safe and efficient operation of nuclear reactors, particularly in the context of selecting new reference rods and optimizing fuel management strategies.

C. Development of the Python-Based Toolkit

In the pursuit of enhancing precision and efficiency in burn-up calculations, the development of a Python-based toolkit represents a significant advancement. This toolkit was designed to complement and improve upon existing methodologies employed by Studsvik, offering a flexible, user-friendly, and robust solution for burn-up calculations.

Methodology: The development process involved selecting a range of test cases representing various reactor types, fuel configurations, and burn-up conditions. Both the Python-based toolkit and Studsvik's existing methodologies were used to perform calculations under identical conditions.

The results were compared based on accuracy, computation time, and usability, with an error analysis conducted to identify discrepancies.

Features and Capabilities: The toolkit includes customizable algorithms that allow users to tailor calculations to specific reactor conditions and fuel types. It integrates seamlessly with existing databases, facilitating easy access to historical data for analysis. An advanced graphical user interface (GUI) simplifies user interaction, as shown in Fig.4, allowing for intuitive input of parameters and visualization of results.

Figure 4: GUI Of Burn-Up Calculation Python-Based Toolkit

Comparative Evaluation: The Python-based toolkit demonstrated high accuracy in burn-up calculations, with results closely aligning with Studsvik’s established methodologies. The comparison is summarized in Table I, which shows that the new toolkit’s results are consistent with verified data from the GUN7 and F3F6 methodologies. The toolkit also offered improved computational efficiency and a better user experience, thanks to its GUI and flexible features.

Parameter	New Toolkit	Verified Results from F3F6
Consumed U235 (%)	90	90
U_f	0.6296	0.63
Pu_f	0.3704	0.37
Decay factor	0.9212	0.9272
Escape probability	0.6336	0.65
FIMA [%]	5.0543	5.06

Table I: Comparative Evaluation of the New Toolkit vs. Verified Results from F3F6.

Results: The Python-based toolkit showed high accuracy in burn-up calculations, with results closely matching Studsvik’s established methods. It also improved computational efficiency, reducing processing times due to Python’s optimized libraries. Users found the advanced GUI intuitive, leading to better usability, and appreciated the toolkit’s flexibility in modeling various reactor scenarios.

III. LOCAL AXIAL BURN-UP DETERMINATION BASED ON GAMMA SCANNING

This part explores different measurement methods for determining burn-up levels, particularly focusing on gamma spectroscopy and other non-destructive techniques. Gamma spectroscopy, utilizing isotopes like Cs-137, is preferred due to its accuracy and non-invasive nature. Advanced tools such as circumferential gamma scanning offer a comprehensive analysis of isotopic distribution within the fuel rods, allowing for improved precision in burn-up measurements.

A. Principles of Burn-up Measurement

Accurate burn-up measurement is fundamental to nuclear reactor operation, as it informs decisions about fuel replacement, reactor performance, and safety protocols. One of the most widely used methods for burn-up measurement involves gamma scan analysis of long-lived fission products, particularly Cesium-137 (Cs-137), which is favored for these calculations due to its relatively long half-life of 30.7 years, which provides a stable and consistent signal over time.

The burn-up calculation process from gamma scan typically involves taking multiple gamma measurements along the length of the fuel rod. The accuracy of these measurements is heavily dependent on the precision of the reference rod used for comparison. The burn-up of the reference rod is compared to that of the target rod, and any discrepancies are adjusted to ensure accurate readings. The accurate gamma measurement instrument and proper correction parameters is vital in such comparative method for ensuring the precise burn-up results, and then leading to efficient fuel use, meeting safety standards, complying with regulatory requirements, and managing fuel reprocessing or disposal. However, achieving precise burn-up measurements is challenging. Differences in the irradiation history, fuel composition, and decay times of the rods can introduce uncertainties. To address these challenges, advanced computational models and correction factors are applied to refine the burn-up calculations.

B. Matching Reference Rods to Different Target Fuel Design

In an ideal scenario, the reference rod used for burn-up calculations would have identical geometric dimensions, enrichment levels, irradiation history, and decay time as the rod being measured. However, achieving such a perfect match is rarely feasible in practice. To overcome this, existing reference rods are used, and corrections are applied to account for differences in irradiation history, decay times, and other variables.

The gamma analysis program first analyzes the gamma radiation emitted from the reference rod, specifically focusing on the 662 keV photons emitted from Cs-137. This analysis corrects for the decay of Cs-137 that occurs after the irradiation period, ensuring that the burn-up calculations remain accurate over time. Furthermore, the program adjusts the burn-up calculations to account for differences in power history, fuel density, cladding thickness, and fuel diameter.

However, the attenuation factor, which is applied to the Cs-137 photons, primarily corrects for physical parameters like cladding thickness and fuel density. It does not directly account for variations in power history or enrichment ratios, as these require separate corrections within the burn-up calculation process.

The overall yield of Cs-137 is further influenced by the ratio of fissions from Uranium (U) and Plutonium (Pu), which can be estimated based on the enrichment and the approximate burn-up. Accurate burn-up measurements are ensured through a combination of these corrections and sophisticated gamma measurement systems, which include Ge coaxial detectors and advanced spectrum analysis software.

C. Method description

The Gamma scan measurement begins with the application of closely spaced point measurements along the length of the irradiated fuel rod. This technique utilizes a high-resolution gamma spectrometry device, which is positioned behind a 0.5 mm tungsten collimator to ensure accurate and focused gamma-ray detection. The gamma spectrum is recorded in increments of 0.25 mm along the rod's axis, allowing for a detailed spatial analysis of the rod's burn-up profile. A key aspect of this technique is the measurement of the gamma peak associated with Cesium-137 (Cs-137), specifically the 661 keV peak. Cs-137 is a well-established fission product whose activity is indicative of the burn-up level. During the scanning process, the intensity of this peak is plotted against the axial position of the rod, creating a profile that reflects the distribution of Cs-137 along the rod. Activity of Cs-137 in Fig.5 provides the following information:

- The activity at the lower and top end parts of the rod are lower.
- The regular dips each 10.0 – 10.25 mm are due to the lower amount of fuel in the pellet/pellet interfaces.

Figure 5: Activity of GUN07 .

The FIMA (Fissions per Initial Metal Atom [%]) values along the rod were calculated by comparing the Cs-137 activity at the end of the irradiation with the Cs-137 activity of a reference rod, with chemically determined FIMA. The reference rod was measured together with the rod. The calculation includes the following factors influencing the Cs-137 activity of the reference rod and the examined rod;

power history, pellet and cladding geometry, ratio of U and Pu fissions, pellet density, elapsed time after irradiation. To ensure accuracy, a reference rod segment with known burn-up characteristics is scanned alongside the rod of interest. The reference segment provides a benchmark against which the activity measurements from the test rod can be compared. By correlating the apparent Cs-137 activity in the reference segment with its decay-corrected activity from prior characterization, a correction factor is established. This factor accounts for discrepancies caused by variations in fission rates, rod geometry, and fuel density, particularly those arising from differences in plutonium content.

The correction factor is crucial for obtaining an accurate measurement of local burn-up in the test rod. The following equation is applied to calculate the local burn-up in the measured rod [8]:

$$FIMA = \frac{a}{a_r} \times \frac{dec_r}{dec} \times \frac{P_r}{P} \times \frac{D_{pr}^2}{D_p^2} \times \frac{\rho_r}{\rho} \times \frac{Pu_r}{Pu} \times FIMA_r, \quad (1)$$

Where the index r refers to the value for the reference rod

- FIMA [%] – fissions per initial metal atom in measured rod
- a [Bq] – apparent activity of Cs-137 at end of the irradiation
- dec – decay factor for Cs-137 during the irradiation
- P – escape probability of 662 keV photons from the rod calculated as described in [9].
- Dp [mm] – pellet diameter
- ρ [g/cm³] – density of the fuel
- Pu – factor $[(Uf*6,22 + Puf*6,67)/6,22]$ representing the higher fission yield of Cs-137 from Pu-239 fissions than for U-235 fissions, Uf and Puf are fraction of U and Pu fissions respectively.

IV. CORRECTION FACTOR(PU FACTOR)

The correction factor is crucial for ensuring that burn-up and FIMA (Fissions per Initial Metal Atom) measurements are accurate and truly reflective of the fuel's condition. This factor is derived by comparing the Cs-137 activity of the reference rod to its decay-corrected activity. By incorporating key data points such as the nominal and post-irradiation weights of uranium and uranium-235 from the transport data sheet, the correction factor helps accurately estimate the enrichment levels and the relative contributions of uranium and plutonium fissions. This process leads to more precise burn-up and FIMA calculations, ensuring that the measurements accurately represent the true fuel conditions. In short, "Pu factor" underscores the transition from uranium to plutonium as the primary source of fission at higher burn-ups, reflecting the increasing role of plutonium in the fuel cycle.

V. DECAY FACTOR EVALUATION

The decay factor is an essential component in adjusting the measured Cs-137 activity to account for its decay over time

during irradiation. Cs-137 has a known decay rate, and its activity diminishes continuously throughout the fuel's time in the reactor. The decay factor (dec) is corrects for this reduction and is computed using the following equation[9]:

$$\text{dec} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{P_i}{\lambda} (1 - e^{-\lambda t_i}) e^{-\lambda [\sum_{k=i+1}^n t_k]}}{1} \quad (2)$$

In the equation, P_i and t_i represent the power and duration for a series of n steps in a simplified irradiation history, respectively. λ is the decay constant for Cs-137. t_k is similar to t_i , but for each i , t_k is summed for all $k > i$ to calculate the decay of the activity formed during the time interval i up to the end of the irradiation. This correction is crucial for accurately reflecting the true amount of Cs-137 present at the end of the irradiation period. In Table II, you can find the previously mentioned parameter values for F3F6, R3D12, and GUN07.

Parameter	F3F6	R3D12	GUN07
U_f	0.629	0.614	0.664
Pu_f	0.370	0.395	0.336
Decay factor	0.929	0.924	0.927
Escape probability	0.650	0.652	0.634
Diameter (outer) [mm]	8.190	8.192	8.760
Density [g/cm^3]	10.510	10.340	10.530
Pellet weight/mm	0.554	0.545	0.635
Activity [Bq]	2.18E+09	2.31E+09	3.93E+09

Table II: Parameters used for calculating burn-up.

A. Principle of Burn-up Determination Based on Radiochemical Analyses

The percent fissions per initial metal atom, FIMA%, is calculated by dividing the number of fissions N_f in the analyzed sample by the sum of heavy metal atoms N_{HM} and the number of fissions [10]

$$\text{FIMA}\% = 100 \times \frac{N_f}{N_{HM} + N_f}, \quad (3)$$

The number of fissions and the number of heavy metals is calculated as follows:

$$N_f = \frac{N_i}{Y_i}, \quad (4)$$

$$N_{HM} = N_U + N_{Pu} + N_{Ac}, \quad (5)$$

- N_i - Number of atoms of burn-up monitor nuclide
- Y_i - Fission yield of burn-up monitor nuclide
- N_U - Number of uranium atoms
- N_{Pu} - Number of plutonium atoms
- N_{Ac} - Number of other actinide atoms (Np,Am,Cm,...)

The number of other actinide atoms N_{Ac} only contributes with a very small amount ($< 0.1\%$) to the total number of heavy metal atoms and might be neglected. Thus, inserting Equations (4) and (5), the equation for FIMA% can be written as follows:

$$\text{FIMA}\% = 100 \times \frac{\frac{N_i}{Y_i}}{N_U + N_{Pu} + \frac{N_i}{Y_i} (+N_{Ac})} \quad (6)$$

This refined equation facilitates accurate burn-up estimation by focusing on the primary contributors to fission and heavy metal content.

B. Fission yields

The determination of fission yields is critical for accurately calculating burn-up. The fractional fission yield of burn-up monitor nuclides is determined based on detailed measurements and is influenced by the fission processes of various isotopes. External laboratories provide this data, which is calculated using the following equation:

$$Y_i = \sum_{j=1}^n (g_j \times Y_j^i) \quad (7)$$

- Y_i - Fission yield of burn-up monitor nuclide
- g_j - Fraction of fissions from ^{235}U , ^{238}U , ^{239}Pu and ^{241}Pu
- Y_j^i - Yield of nuclide i in fission of nuclide j

These calculations account for the varying contributions of different fissile materials and ensure precise quantification of fission products. Accurate fission yields are essential for determining the burn-up and evaluating the fuel's operational history.

C. Burn-up as MWd/kgU

For 200 MeV per fission, the factor to transform FIMA% into MWd/kgU is 9.384 MWd/kgU per FIMA% [11]. The neutron spectrum, irradiation history, burn-up, and initial ^{235}U enrichment ratio are related to the average amount of energy released per fission in the irradiated fuel. Calculations have been performed for a typical BWR spectrum and irradiation history as a basis for a table to estimate released energy per fission for an initial enrichment between 1.5 and 5 % and a burn-up of up to 72 MWd/kgU [12]. For example, at an initial enrichment of 4.95% and a burn-up of 63 MWd/kgU, the energy released per fission is approximately 205.1 MeV. Applying this to the conversion factor gives:

$$9.384 \times \frac{205.1}{200} = 9.623 \frac{\text{MWd}}{\text{kgU}} / \text{FIMA}\% \quad (8)$$

This adjusted conversion factor accounts for variations in energy release and provides a more accurate representation of burn-up in terms of MWd/kgU. By applying this factor, radiochemical analyses yield precise and reliable burn-up values, crucial for fuel performance assessments and nuclear fuel cycle management.

VI. CALCULATIONS AND RESULTS

This section presents the results of burn-up, with a focus on circumferential gamma scanning and benchmarking with reference rods. Moreover, the benchmarking of the GUN7 rod against established reference rods (F3F6 and R3D12) yielded

valuable insights. This comparative analysis underscores the effectiveness of the selected methodology in delivering precise and consistent burn-up calculations, further enhancing our understanding of fuel performance and supporting improved fuel management practices.

A. Circumferential Gamma Scanning

Circumferential gamma scanning is a non-destructive technique used to assess the isotopic distribution of the source, and instrument in Studsvik can circumferentially scan the fuel at multiple locations sequentially. This method involves rotating the fuel rod while measuring gamma radiation at various angles around the rod's circumference using high-purity Germanium (HPGe) detectors. The collected data yields a detailed isotopic profile, which is essential for identifying any asymmetries, hot spots, or defects in the fuel, reflecting the fuel usage history.

In the case of the R3D12 reference rod, circumferential gamma scanning was conducted at five specific axial positions: 1772 mm, 1822 mm, 1871 mm, 1921 mm, and 1971 mm. The results, illustrated in Fig. 6, show the gamma radiation profiles at these positions. The examination revealed that the R3D12 rod exhibited superior isotopic uniformity and consistent burn-up characteristics across all scanned positions. These findings suggest that R3D12 is highly suitable as a reference rod.

Figure 6: Circumferential Gamma Scanning for R3D12 with five different positions

This methodology is grounded in established research. Demonstrated the effectiveness of gamma-ray scanning systems in measuring irradiated nuclear fuel [4]. The measurement's standard deviation across five different positions is 0.01. The application of circumferential gamma scanning in this study ensures that the selected reference rod will enhance the accuracy and reliability of burn-up results.

B. Benchmark New Reference Rod

The GUN7 rod is chosen for benchmarking the new reference rod because its burn-up (BU) has been thoroughly verified and documented in the internationally recognized SCIP IV (Studsvik Cladding Integrity Program) project. The burn-up data from GUN7 has undergone rigorous validation, making it a trustworthy data point.

1) *Results for GUN07 using F3F6:* The measurements are performed using a Ge-detector and a 0.5 mm collimator. The gamma spectra are measured and analyzed at equidistant positions (0.25 mm) axially along the rod. The activity of selected isotopes is stored and can be plotted as a function of axial position. Axial adjustments to maintain the correct pellet length across the cuts are made. The fuel stack length can be evaluated from the Cs-137 activity graph.

Results are presented in Fig. 7, which shows the relative activity for Cs-137 for rod F3F6. Cs-137 is created by fissions of uranium (U) and plutonium (Pu), and the overall axial distribution thus represents the thermal neutron axial distribution. The FIMA value [%] is then converted based on 9.384 MWd/kgU/%FIMA for an energy/fission of 200 MeV. The energy/fission for the calculated burn-up for the rod in question gives the value 9.62 MWd/kgU/%FIMA. These results are calculated using the data in Table A1 in the Appendix and a visual representation of these data is shown in Fig. 7

Figure 7: Cs-137 Activity Graph Comparing F3F6 Reference Rod (a) and GUN7 (b)

The FIMA value [%] is then converted to burn-up in MWd/kgU by multiplying it by 7.18 MWd/kgU/%FIMA. The evaluated burn-up profile together with the rod average burn-up is presented in Fig. 8. The rod has an evaluated average burn-up of 67.07 MWd/kgU, which is 0.07 higher than verified result.

Figure 8: Burn-up Analysis for GUN7 Using F3F6 Reference Rod

2) *Results for GUN07 using D3R12:* For GUN07 is calculated using R3D12 as a reference rod. Same Ge-detector and a 0.5 mm collimator were used as in the previous analysis. The Cs-137 activity profile for the GUN07 rod compared to the R3D12 reference rod is shown in Fig.4.4. Information on the fission distribution of Uranium (U) and Plutonium (Pu), as well as the distribution of thermal neutrons, is obtained from the Cs-137 activity. The FIMA (Fissions per Initial Metal Atom) values were determined by comparing the Cs-137 activity in the GUN07 rod with that in the R3D12 reference rod. The FIMA values were converted using a reference factor of 9.384 MWd/kgU/%FIMA, corresponding to an energy release of 200 MeV per fission. This conversion provided a reliable estimate of the burn-up for the GUN07 rod.

Results are presented in Fig. 9, which shows the relative activity for Cs-137 for rod F3F6. Cs-137 is created by fissions of uranium (U) and plutonium (Pu), and the overall axial distribution thus represents the thermal neutron axial distribution. The FIMA value [%] is then converted based on 9.384 MWd/kgU/%FIMA for an energy/fission of 200 MeV. The energy/fission for the calculated burn-up for the rod in question gives the value 9.62 MWd/kgU/%FIMA. These results are derived from the data presented in Table A2 in the Appendix, with a visual representation provided in Fig.9.

Figure 9: Cs-137 Activity Graph Comparing F3F6 Reference Rod (a) and GUN7 (b)

The FIMA value [%] is then converted to burn-up in MWd/kgU by multiplying it by 7.18 MWd/kgU/%FIMA. The evaluated burn-up profile together with the rod average burn-up is presented in Fig. 10. The rod has an evaluated average

burn-up of 67.07 MWd/kgU, which is 0.07 higher than verified result.

Figure 10: Burn-up Analysis for GUN7 Using F3F6 Reference Rod

3) *Comparative Analysis:* The comparison between the F3F6 and R3D12 reference rods used for the GUN07 rod burn-up calculations showed that there was a small difference between them verified result. This difference is within the acceptable margin of error 2% [13]. Table III shows that there is a minor value difference of 67.1 MWd/kgU for R3D12 and 67.07 MWd/kgU for F3F6. This difference is acceptable and demonstrates the potential of R3D12 to provide consistent results for burn-up calculations.

	Burn-up (MWd/kgU)	Difference (MWd/kgU)
Verified GUN07 Result	67.00	-
GUN07 from F3F6	67.07	-0.07
GUN07 from R3D12	67.10	-0.10

Table III: Burn-up Differences for GUN07 using F3F6 and R3D12

The small deviation of R3D12 from the verified result indicates that it is a suitable reference rod for new burn-up calculations. The reason for the difference observed in Table 4.1 is the difference in the parameters shown in Tab. III when calculating the burn-up value of GUN07.

VII. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSION

The selection of the R3D12 rod as the new reference rod for burn-up calculations marks a significant advancement in meeting the needs of rods came from modern reactor designs. A detailed evaluation of R3D12 showed that it exhibited similar isotopic homogeneity and combustion characteristics to F3F6, which was previously used as a reference rod. These improvements are essential for the accuracy and reliability of combustion assessments.

However, further work is necessary to optimize the application of R3D12 across various reactor configurations and operational conditions. Future research should focus on validating R3D12's performance under a wider range of reactor types and burn-up levels, ensuring its robustness and versatility as a reference rod. Additionally, radiochemical analyses, in particular, can provide precise measurements of isotopic concentrations, offering a valuable tool for verifying and complementing gamma scanning results, thereby enhancing the

overall accuracy of burn-up calculations. Though not reaching the release quality to be practically used, the toolkit developed in the study currently is a pioneer tool. Potentially it has the function to automate the burn-up calculation with the built-in guidance to user, which can drastically reduce the human error in manually copy and paste in data sheets in many aspects. Furthermore, the compatibility of python can provide future capacity to be integrated or connected to other IT interfaces.

In summary, the adoption of the R3D12 rod represents a critical improvement in burn-up calculations, with the potential to significantly boost efficiency. Nevertheless, ongoing research and development, including the application of radio-chemical analyses, are essential to fully realize the benefits of this new reference rod and to address emerging challenges in nuclear fuel management.

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VIII. APPENDIX

Table A1

The results obtained with the reference rods used for burn-up calculations of the target rod are shown in Table A1 and Table A2. In Table A1, the burn-up values of the GUN7 rod are calculated using F3F6.

Distance from rod bottom (mm)	Bottom (mm)	Cs-137 (Bq)	BU [MWd/kgU]
433.688	177.329	3.99×10^9	68.1
433.938	177.578	3.94×10^9	67.4
434.189	177.829	3.95×10^9	67.4
434.438	178.078	3.98×10^9	68.0
434.688	178.328	3.97×10^9	67.8
434.939	178.579	3.99×10^9	68.1
435.190	178.830	3.99×10^9	68.2
435.438	179.078	3.97×10^9	67.9
435.690	179.330	3.96×10^9	67.6
435.939	179.579	3.94×10^9	67.2
436.188	179.828	3.97×10^9	67.8
436.440	180.080	3.97×10^9	67.7
436.689	180.329	3.93×10^9	67.1
436.938	180.578	3.92×10^9	66.9
437.191	180.831	3.92×10^9	67.0
437.439	181.080	3.94×10^9	67.2
437.689	181.329	3.94×10^9	67.3
437.940	181.580	3.94×10^9	67.3
438.190	181.830	3.95×10^9	67.4
438.439	182.079	3.92×10^9	66.9
438.690	182.330	3.95×10^9	67.5
438.940	182.580	4.03×10^9	68.8
439.190	182.830	3.93×10^9	67.1
439.440	183.080	3.97×10^9	67.9
439.689	183.329	3.96×10^9	67.6
439.941	183.581	3.93×10^9	67.1
440.190	183.830	3.99×10^9	68.1
440.439	184.079	3.95×10^9	67.5
440.692	184.332	3.96×10^9	67.7

Table A1 (continued)

Distance from rod bottom (mm)	Bottom (mm)	Cs-137 (Bq)	BU [MWd/kgU]
440.941	184.581	3.90×10^9	66.6
441.190	184.830	3.94×10^9	67.3
441.443	185.083	3.90×10^9	66.5
441.690	185.330	3.95×10^9	67.5
441.940	185.580	3.92×10^9	66.9
442.193	185.833	3.84×10^9	65.6
442.441	186.081	3.67×10^9	62.7
442.692	186.332	3.79×10^9	64.7
442.943	186.583	3.87×10^9	66.2
443.192	186.832	4.00×10^9	68.3
443.442	187.082	3.92×10^9	67.0
443.693	187.333	3.95×10^9	67.5
443.943	187.583	3.94×10^9	67.3
444.193	187.833	3.95×10^9	67.5
444.442	188.082	3.91×10^9	66.8
444.692	188.332	3.96×10^9	67.6
444.944	188.584	3.93×10^9	67.1
445.194	188.834	3.92×10^9	67.0
445.442	189.082	4.01×10^9	68.4
445.695	189.335	3.91×10^9	66.8
445.943	189.583	3.95×10^9	67.5
446.192	189.832	3.95×10^9	67.5
446.445	190.085	3.94×10^9	67.3
446.693	190.333	3.90×10^9	66.6
446.943	190.583	3.92×10^9	67.0
447.195	190.836	3.93×10^9	67.1
447.444	191.084	3.95×10^9	67.5
447.693	191.333	3.95×10^9	67.4
447.945	191.585	3.93×10^9	67.2
448.194	191.834	3.97×10^9	67.8
448.444	192.084	3.89×10^9	66.4

Table A1 (continued)

Distance from rod bottom (mm)	Bottom (mm)	Cs-137 (Bq)	BU [MWd/kgU]
448.695	192.335	3.96×10^9	67.6
448.944	192.585	3.95×10^9	67.4
449.195	192.835	3.95×10^9	67.4
449.444	193.085	3.94×10^9	67.2
449.694	193.335	3.91×10^9	66.9
449.946	193.586	3.90×10^9	66.7
450.196	193.836	3.91×10^9	66.9
450.443	194.084	3.90×10^9	66.7
450.696	194.336	3.89×10^9	66.4
450.945	194.585	3.97×10^9	67.8
451.194	194.834	3.89×10^9	66.5
451.447	195.087	3.95×10^9	67.4
451.695	195.335	3.91×10^9	66.7
451.945	195.585	3.73×10^9	63.8
452.196	195.836	3.80×10^9	64.9
452.445	196.086	3.93×10^9	67.1
452.696	196.336	3.92×10^9	67.0
452.946	196.587	3.85×10^9	65.8
453.196	196.836	3.90×10^9	66.6
453.446	197.086	3.88×10^9	66.2
453.697	197.337	3.86×10^9	65.9
453.946	197.586	3.89×10^9	68.3
454.197	197.837	3.91×10^9	68.6
454.447	198.087	3.89×10^9	68.3
454.696	198.336	3.88×10^9	68.2
454.949	198.589	3.90×10^9	68.5
455.198	198.838	3.87×10^9	67.9
455.446	199.086	3.90×10^9	68.4
455.699	199.339	3.91×10^9	68.7
455.947	199.587	3.94×10^9	69.2

Table A2

In Table A2, the burn-up values of the GUN7 rod are calculated using R3D12.

Distance from rod bottom (mm)	Bottom (mm)	Cs-137 (Bq)	BU [MWd/kgU]
433.689	177.329	3.77×10^9	64.52
433.938	177.578	3.85×10^9	65.88
434.189	177.829	3.99×10^9	68.16
434.438	178.078	3.94×10^9	67.41
434.688	178.328	3.95×10^9	67.44
434.939	178.579	3.98×10^9	68.06
435.190	178.830	3.97×10^9	67.90
435.438	179.078	3.99×10^9	68.15
435.690	179.330	3.99×10^9	68.23
435.939	179.579	3.97×10^9	67.93
436.188	179.828	3.96×10^9	67.66
436.440	180.080	3.94×10^9	67.29
436.689	180.329	3.97×10^9	67.84
436.938	180.578	3.97×10^9	67.78
437.191	180.831	3.93×10^9	67.12
437.439	181.080	3.92×10^9	66.95
437.689	181.329	3.92×10^9	67.03
437.940	181.580	3.94×10^9	67.29
438.190	181.830	3.94×10^9	67.38
438.439	182.079	3.94×10^9	67.39
438.690	182.330	3.95×10^9	67.48
438.940	182.580	3.92×10^9	66.96
439.190	182.830	3.95×10^9	67.53
439.440	183.080	4.03×10^9	68.81
439.689	183.329	3.93×10^9	67.12
439.941	183.581	3.97×10^9	67.93
440.190	183.830	3.96×10^9	67.61
440.439	184.079	3.93×10^9	67.19
440.692	184.332	3.99×10^9	68.14
440.941	184.581	3.95×10^9	67.58
441.190	184.830	3.96×10^9	67.77

Table A2 (continued)

Distance from rod bottom (mm)	Bottom (mm)	Cs-137 (Bq)	BU [MWd/kgU]
441.443	185.083	3.89×10^9	66.62
441.690	185.330	3.94×10^9	67.34
441.940	185.580	3.89×10^9	66.58
442.193	185.833	3.95×10^9	67.52
442.441	186.081	3.92×10^9	66.94
442.692	186.332	3.84×10^9	65.68
442.943	186.583	3.67×10^9	62.71
443.192	186.832	3.79×10^9	64.71
443.442	187.082	3.87×10^9	66.21
443.693	187.333	3.99×10^9	68.32
443.943	187.583	3.92×10^9	67.00
444.193	187.833	3.95×10^9	67.53
444.442	188.082	3.93×10^9	67.33
444.692	188.332	3.95×10^9	67.52
444.944	188.584	3.91×10^9	66.87
445.194	188.834	3.96×10^9	67.67
445.442	189.082	3.93×10^9	67.14
445.695	189.335	3.92×10^9	67.01
445.943	189.583	4.00×10^9	68.46
446.192	189.832	3.91×10^9	66.83
446.445	190.085	3.95×10^9	67.55
446.693	190.333	3.95×10^9	67.51
446.943	190.583	3.94×10^9	67.36
447.195	190.836	3.90×10^9	66.69
447.444	191.084	3.92×10^9	67.02
447.693	191.333	3.93×10^9	67.10
447.945	191.585	3.95×10^9	67.54
448.194	191.834	3.95×10^9	67.46
448.444	192.084	3.93×10^9	67.25
448.695	192.335	3.97×10^9	67.84
448.944	192.585	3.89×10^9	66.45
449.195	192.835	3.96×10^9	67.62

Table A2 (continued)

Distance from rod bottom (mm)	Bottom (mm)	Cs-137 (Bq)	BU [MWd/kgU]
449.444	193.085	3.95×10^9	67.48
449.694	193.335	3.95×10^9	67.50
449.946	193.586	3.94×10^9	67.28
450.196	193.836	3.91×10^9	66.90
450.443	194.084	3.90×10^9	66.70
450.696	194.336	3.91×10^9	66.92
450.945	194.585	3.90×10^9	66.70
451.194	194.834	3.89×10^9	66.44
451.447	195.087	3.97×10^9	67.89
451.695	195.335	3.89×10^9	66.58
451.945	195.585	3.95×10^9	67.45
452.196	195.836	3.91×10^9	66.79
452.445	196.086	3.73×10^9	63.83
452.696	196.336	3.80×10^9	64.96
452.946	196.587	3.93×10^9	67.19
453.196	196.836	3.92×10^9	67.00
453.446	197.086	3.85×10^9	65.88
453.697	197.337	3.90×10^9	66.67